

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONSCIOUSNESS AND THE TEACHING
OF CONCEPTS OF THE UNCONSCIOUS TO STUDENTS**

Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna

Assistant Professor of Asian International University

Abstract: Broadly researching the concept of early consciousness in psychology, this concept expands the scope of creative thinking between knowledge, skill acquisition, and interpretation of the concept of consciousness in controversial conversations among students.

Key words: Consciousness, unconsciousness, psyche, matter, brain, phenomenon, personality, materialism.

Consciousness is the highest form of mental activity. It is only a human phenomenon. The question of consciousness, its essence, is one of the most ancient problems. At first, they tried to explain consciousness within the framework of religious and mythological views. The religious explanation of consciousness is based on interpreting it as a divine phenomenon, a miracle created by God. In many religions, human consciousness is described as a manifestation of the great divine intelligence. Although the roots of such views are very ancient, they still have many supporters. He who admits that the universe and man are created, considers that Consciousness is also the power of creation.

The 2nd direction in explaining the nature of consciousness is to understand consciousness as a reflection of the material world in the human brain, to interpret it in connection with the activity of the human body. At the same time, cases of distorting the essence of Consciousness appeared within the framework of such approaches, which were named the materialistic direction. According to the current known as vulgar materialism, the brain produces Consciousness just as the liver produces bile. This approach leads to the conclusion that Consciousness is not an ideal, but a material phenomenon. Although bile can be seen, Consciousness cannot be seen or grasped. In fact, the history of Consciousness is related to the history of the human being. Since man is both a biological and a social being, then Consciousness is a product of both biological and social development. Consciousness is made up of human thoughts and feelings, sensations, imaginations, will and views. Self-awareness, memory, will, speech are the main aspects of Consciousness.

Modern science recognizes that Consciousness is the result of a long evolution of matter. Matter, nature has always existed, and man is a product of relatively recent development of the material world. It took several million years for the development of matter and the emergence of a person who can think. Consciousness is a product of natural development, a property of matter, not of all matter, but of highly

organized matter, that is, the human brain. But the existence of the brain alone is not enough for Consciousness. Consciousness is closely connected with the natural and social environment that surrounds a person and can act under the influence of this environment.

Nowadays, electronic machines have been created that also perform complex creative processes, but they cannot replace Consciousness, because Consciousness is a very complex objective entity.

And states that occur without the participation of consciousness. Unconsciousness is often manifested in body movement, memory, imagination. It occurs in response effects caused by real but imperceptible stimuli, in actions that are originally conscious and become automatic as a result of repetition, and in other situations. For example, a person returns home immersed in his thoughts, and in any case comes without going astray. If he perceives a danger, he will take a protective action even before he understands the cause and nature of this danger. Pathological phenomena such as delusions, hallucinations, sleep, during hypnosis, lunaticism and sleeplessness that occur in the patient's psyche. mental activity that occurs during 3. Freud interprets the Unconscious in a purely irrational way. According to him, there is an irreconcilable opposition between consciousness and the Unconscious. Human behavior is determined by this contradiction. A person does not dare to understand and notice the unconsciousness, it is the place of eternal desires in a person.

CONCEPT OF CONSCIOUSNESS.

Psyche is a reflection of reality in a person's brain and differs in different degrees.

The highest level of psyche characteristic of a person is consciousness. Consciousness is the form of the psyche that unites it into a whole and is the result of the social and historical conditions of the formation of a person in his labor activity, in the process of communicating with others using language. In this sense, the mind is nothing more than the existence that the classics of Marxism understood as a social product.

What is the structure of consciousness, its important psychological definition.

Its first definition is given in its name itself, which means consciousness. A person's mind is composed of a complex of knowledge about the world around us. K. Marx. "Knowledge is the way in which the mind lives, and the existence of something for the mind." he wrote. The structure of consciousness includes important cognitive processes. With their help, a person constantly enriches his knowledge. These processes include sensations and perception, memory, imagination and thinking. As a result of the direct reflection of the observers affecting the brain with the help of sensations and perception, the emotional picture of the existence formed

in the imagination of a person at that moment is embodied in the mind. Memory recreates images of the past in the mind. Imagination creates a figurative model of something that is the object of need but is not present at the moment. Thinking provides a solution to a problem based on generalized knowledge. It leads to the complete failure of any one of the aforementioned psychic cognition processes.

The second definition of consciousness is that it expresses a clear distinction between the subject and the object, that is, what is related to the concept of "I". Man, who was the first in the history of the world of living organisms to stand out and set himself against his environment, keeps this conflict and difference in his mind.

Among living beings, he is the only one capable of self-knowledge, that is, of directing his mental activity to self-research. Man consciously evaluates his actions and himself in general. The separation of "I" into "not me" is a process that everyone experiences in childhood, and it happens in the process of self-realization.

The third definition of consciousness is the provision of purposeful human activity. The creation of activity goals is part of the function of the mind. In this, the motivations of the activity arise and are estimated. Voluntary decisions are made. How the actions are performed is taken into account. Appropriate corrections will be made to it and so on.

K. Marx "is not limited to changing the form of what is given by man, but also realizes his conscious purpose with what is given by nature. This goal, as a law, defines a person's work method and the character of this work, and a person should subordinate his will to this goal.

In the performance and direction of purposeful activities due to illness or any other reason should be considered as a disturbance of consciousness.

The fourth definition of consciousness is that it contains certain attitudes. "My attitude to my environment is my mind," wrote K. Marx.

The world of feelings inevitably enters the mind of a person, in which a complex lens is reflected, first of all, social relations in which he is involved. Here, as in many other (involved) social cases, pathology helps to understand the nature of normal consciousness. When suffering from certain mental illnesses, the disorder of consciousness is determined by the disorder in the field of emotions and relationships:

The patient does not like his mother, whom he loved so much. That is, he talks about people with sarcasm and hakazo.

Language is an indispensable condition for the manifestation of all the above-mentioned specific characteristics and formation of consciousness. A person creates knowledge in the activity of the speech process. Before a person comes into the world, he enriches his life with the human thinking and wealth that is conveyed to

him in the language created for him by humanity. AI Hertsen wrote: "Everyone is rooted in a terrible family tree that goes back to ancient times: behind us, like a wave on the shore, we feel the intensity of the entire ocean - the history of the whole world: at this moment in our brains all the ideas of the ages... language, a separate lens, a system that reflects social historical experience or social consciousness. As long as it is mastered by the concrete person, the language becomes in a certain sense his real consciousness .

Great thinkers noted that "Language is a practical, real consciousness, because it exists for others, it exists for me as well...". The concept of consciousness in psychology. In psychiatry and other sciences, it is used in a sense that corresponds to the basic definitions given above.

Psychiatrists are always interested in the question of whether the patient has consciousness, or whether it is impaired, so when they say consciousness, the patient's personal situation about where he is, when, what the surrounding situation is. they also understand the possibilities of reporting on their actions. A well-preserved person evaluates the new information coming to the brain, taking into account the existing knowledge , and separates himself from the surrounding environment, maintains a structured system of relationships with other people, activities and situations, and based on all this information controls his behavior . Consciousness is a social product and unique to humans. Animals do not have consciousness. The lower level of the psyche consists of the unconscious.

Unconsciousness is a set of mental processes and situations associated with impressions that make a person unable to control himself. As a mental state, unconsciousness is a form of reflection of reality , in which targeting the place and time of action, its integrity is lost, control of behavior with the help of speech is disturbed. The following mental states can be included in the unconscious: mental phenomena occurring during sleep (dreaming) responses to observers that are imperceptible but actually affect them: they were previously conscious actions, but became repetitive and automatic, and therefore are now It is also possible to see some protological phenomena occurring in the patient's psyche, such as some protological phenomena occurring in the patient's psyche, such as some inclinations to the activity of actions that have become incomprehensible but are not understood by the sense of purpose, such as the appearance of things that are not there in the eyes. based on these , it would be wrong to consider unconsciousness as opposed to consciousness, to equate it with the psyche of animals.

Unconsciousness is a specific mental image of a person, like consciousness, which is in the brain of a person who is not sufficiently homogeneous, but in a way that is related to the social conditions of a person's life.

References

1. Ikromova, S. (2023). INTERPRETATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY FACTOR IN RELATION TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 390-394.
2. Ikromova, S. (2023). CONCEPT OF IDEOLOGY AND FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY IN YOUTH STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(6), 1223-1226.
3. Ikromova, S. (2023). FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN TEENAGERS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1009-1014.
4. Ikromova, S. A. (2022). MILLIY VA DINIY QADRIYATLARNING INSON TARBIYASIDAGI O'RNI. *Экономика и социум*, (12-2 (103)), 675-678.
5. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). SHAXS OG 'ISHGAN XULQINING KO 'RINISHLARI VA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARNING KO 'RINISHLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 528-532.
6. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). YOSHLARDA DESTRUKTIV G'OYALARGA QARSHI IMMUNITET HOSIL QILISH OMILLARI.
7. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). TALABA YOSHLARDA MAFKURA TUSHUNCHASI VA MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITETNI SHAKLLANTIRISH.
8. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). O'SMIRLARDA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH.
9. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH IJTIMOY MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Barqaror Taraqqiyot va Rivojlanish Tamoyillari*, 1(6), 26-29.
10. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). MILLIY HARAKATLI O'YINLARNING BOLALAR TARBIYASIDAGI IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.
11. Sitara Akbarovna Ikromova. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 50-54.
12. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Study of the Formation of Ideological Immunity By Foreign and Russian Researchers. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 235-239.
13. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Adolescence during Destructive Behavior Appearances the Problem Learning Condition. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 105-109.

14. Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna. (2023). NEUROPHYSIOLOGY BASIS OF HORMONES. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 68–77.
15. Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna. (2023). RESEARCH METHODS OF YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
16. Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information in Adolescents. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 119–122.
17. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PYTHON (PYTORCH). Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research , 1(3), 123-126.
18. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ADVANTAGES OF DJANGO FEMWORKER. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
19. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYA YO ‘NALISHIDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN TALABALARGA SPSS YORDAMIDA MATEMATIK USULLARNI O‘RGATISHNING METODIK USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 323-326.
20. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PYTHON INSTRUMENTLARI BILAN KATTA MA’LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 320-322.
21. Jalolov, T. S., & Usmonov, A. U. (2021). “AQLLI ISSIQXONA” BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA TADQIQ QILISH. Экономика и социум, (9 (88)), 74-77.
22. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023). Capabilities of SPSS Software in High Volume Data Processing Testing. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 82-86.
23. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023, November). IDENTIFYING THE POSITIVE EFFECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL WORK FACTORS BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS AND DEPARTMENTS THROUGH SPSS SOFTWARE. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 18, pp. 150-153).
24. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). TEACHING THE BASICS OF PYTHON PROGRAMMING. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).

25. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). Solving Complex Problems in Python. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 481-484.
26. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DATA PROCESSING USING THE SPSS PROGRAM. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(23), 220-223.
27. Tursunbek Sadridinovich Jalolov. (2023). SPSS YOKI IJTIMOIY FANLAR UCHUN STATISTIK PAKET BILAN PSIXOLOGIK MA'LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. Journal of Universal Science Research, 1(12), 207–215.
28. Кутбединов, А. (1985). Разработка и применение ядерно-физических методов анализа подземных вод для выявления предвестников землетрясений.
29. Bahodirovna, S. N. (2023). FORMS OF ORGANIZATION OF MATHEMATICS TEACHING IN ELEMENTARY GRADES. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 10(11), 5-8
30. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2021). ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ КЛАССНЫХ УРОКОВ. Вестник науки и образования, (15-3 (118)), 40-42.
31. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ДИДАКТИЧЕСКОГО ПРОГРАММНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ МАТЕМАТИКЕ. In НОВЫЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ (pp. 10-12).
32. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫМ НАУКАМ. Universum: технические науки, (4-1 (109)), 41-43.
33. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). ВАЖНОСТЬ МАТЕМАТИКИ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК ДЛЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ: Сайфуллаева Нозима Баходировна, преподаватель кафедры “Теория начального образования”, Бухарский государственный университет. Город Бухара. Республика Узбекистан. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (1), 305-307.
34. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). Методы Организации Уроков Математики В Начальных Классах С Использованием Цифровых Технологий. Miasto Przyszłości, 35, 388-390.
35. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2023). РОЛЬ МАТЕМАТИКИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ. PEDAGOGS journali, 1(1), 292-292.

36. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2019). Роль дидактических игр в умственном развитии учащихся в математике начального класса. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY (pp. 102-106).

37. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Марданова, Ф. Я. (2021). НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ ПО ВЫСШЕЙ МАТЕМАТИКЕ. Проблемы науки, 84.

38. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2020). Важные особенности дидактических игр в процессе обучения математике в начальных школах. In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ (pp. 60-62).

39. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Мурадова, Я. М. (2020). Пути эффективного использования методов обучения математике в начальных классах. In EUROPEAN RESEARCH (pp. 121-123).

40. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2022). Методы определения потребностей обучающихся в процессе использования облачных технологий в образовании. Universum: технические науки, (2-1 (95)), 57-59.

41. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Саидова, Г. Э. (2019). Повышение эффективности занятий, используя интерактивные методы в начальном образовании. Научный журнал, (6 (40)), 101-102.